

RECURSION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6546328>

Tojiboyeva Shakhzoda,
NamCU

There are various issues in the Olympiads in Computer Science. In particular, one of them is a recursive issue. If a program uses itself as a procedure or function, such programs are called recursive programs. There are two types of recursive programs:

- a) Correct recursion. In this case, the function is self-contained.
- b) Adjacent recursion. In this case, function 1 refers to function 2, and function 2 refers to function 1.

To write a recursive program, first of all 1) recursive attitude; 2) The initial condition for this relationship must be determined. A recursive relationship is a relationship that connects steps N and $N-1$ of a process. For example, $N! = N(N-1)!$ formula $N!$ can be viewed as a recursive attitude. This is the starting point for a relationship, $1! = 1$ serves. Given this information, the recurrent relationship for a factorial calculation is:

$$N! = \begin{cases} N \cdot (N-1)!, & \text{if } N > 1 \\ 1, & \text{if } N = 1 \end{cases}$$

Apparently, $N!$ first to calculate $(N-1)!$ must be calculated. But, $(N-1)!$ $(N-2)!$ $(N-1)!$, so it's $N-2!$ will be tried. $(N-2)!$ while $(N-3)!$ $(N-2)!$ and so on. So, $N!$ The computational algorithm is "sinking" into itself. This process takes place until the initial state, i.e. $1!$ lasts until. After that, the "sinking" process will stop, $1!$ The computer, which was instructed to be 1 , will now "float" upwards. YA, $2!$ 1 , and so on. This is the case to $N!$ will continue until calculated. The program of this process in Turbo Pascal is written as follows:

```
program factorial ;
  var r,n: integer ;
  function fak(k:integer): integer;
  begin
    if k>1 then fak:=fak(k-1)*k else fak:=1 ;
  end;
  begin
    read(n) ;
    write(fak(n));
  end.
```

In the next problem, the values of the function $f(n)$ are found using the expressions $f(0) = 1$, $f(2n) = f(n)$ and $f(2n+1) = f(n) + 1$. Find $f(k)$ for a given natural number k .

Solution Idea: Solving the above problem using an array of K elements seems like an easy way to most people. But this is not the right thing to do. This is because if K is a large enough number, an array of K elements may not fit in the computer's memory. Plus, not all of these elements work, even when squeezed. When k is 1000, only 11 of the 1000 elements of the array are needed to solve the problem. The rest of the computer's memory is wasted. Therefore, it is best to solve the problem without using an array. This method is a method of using recursion. The fact that the recursive approach and the initial case for this relationship are given in the context of the problem makes the programmer's job easier. In the Turbo Pascal program:

```
Program rekursiya ;
  var k,n : integer ;
  function f(m:integer) : integer ;
```



```

    var h: integer;
begin
    if m=0 then f:=1 else
begin
    h:=m div 2 ;
    if m mod 2=0 then f:=f(h) else f:=f(h)+1;
end;
end;
begin
    read(k) ; n:=f(k) ;
    write('f(',k,') ',n:10)
end.

```

The computer that performs this program for k 10 displays f (10) 3 entries on the display screen.

In the next problem, we will consider the calculation of arithmetic progression using a mathematical formula.

The idea of solving. If we pay attention to the formula, periodically adding d (limit difference), recursive problems must be taken into account. Now we can build a recursive algorithm.

$$Arif(a_1, d, n) = \begin{cases} a_1 & \text{if } n = 1 \\ Arif(a_1, d, n - 1) + d & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

The function can be recorded in the program as follows. In the Turbo Pascal programming environment:

```

Function Arif (a1, d: real; n: integer): real;
Begin
    if n = 1 then Arif := a1 else Arif := Arif(a1, d, n - 1) + d;
End;

```

Apply recursion to the graphics to create a beautiful landscape. For example, to describe a piece of snow in a Turbo Pascal programming environment, the program is as follows:

```

program qor;
uses graph, crt;
var x,y,r,d,m:integer;
    pi:real;
procedure ris(x,y,r:integer);
var x1,y1,t:integer;
begin
    if r<=1 then begin putpixel(x,y,15);exit end;
    for t:=0 to 6 do begin
        x1:=x+trunc(r*cos(t*pi/3)); y1:=y+trunc(r*sin(t*pi/3));
        line(x,y,x1,y1); ris(x1,y1,r*2 div 5);
    end;
end;
begin
d:=detect; initgraph(d,m,'bgi');
pi:=3.14; x:=320; y:=240; r:=80;
ris(x,y,r);
end.

```

When the program starts, the following snowflake image is generated.

From the above, it can be seen that recursion is a more complex concept than a simple procedure or function, but it can be a very good tool in the hands of a skilled programmer.

REFERENCES:

1. <http://th-algoritmov.narod.ru/>
2. <http://www.pascal.ru/pascal/underprog/recursia/>
3. <http://dic.academic.ru/dic.nsf/ruwiki/6791>

